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A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW ON FUTURE PROSPECTS FOR FAST DISSOLVING ORAL FILMS

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ABSTRACT

The ultimate goal of any drug delivery system is the successful delivery of the drug to the body, however patient compliance must not be overlooked. Oral drug delivery is the most widely utilized route of administration among the entire route that has been explored for the systemic delivery of drug via various pharmaceutical products of different dosage forms. With conventional tablet dosage forms, poor patient compliance can be observed especially in case of paediatrics and geriatrics patients, who experience difficulties in swallowing. In response to this mouth dissolving drug delivery system (MDDs) was developed as an alternative to the tablets & capsules. Mouth dissolving films (MDF) are the novel dosage forms that disintegrate and dissolve rapidly within the oral cavity. Intra-oral absorption permits rapid onset of action and helps by-pass first-pass effects, thereby reducing the unit dose required to produce desired therapeutic effect. The present review provides an overview of recent advancements, manufacturing methods and various polymers used in the manufacture of mouth dissolving film.

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INTRODUCTION

Among the various routes of drug delivery, the oral route is the most acceptable for the patients [1]. Many pharmaceutical companies have directed their research activity in reformulating existing drugs into new dosage forms. One such relatively new dosage form is the oral strip, a thin film that is prepared by using hydrophilic polymers that rapidly dissolves on the tongue or buccal cavity. Developing formulations for children has been a challenging task. Amongst other factors, palatability of formulations for pediatric oral medications is one of the most significant factors influencing compliance to therapeutic regimens [2]. Although solid dosage forms are widely accepted by elders and adolescents, younger children tend to prefer liquid formulations that are easier to swallow. Keeping the ease of administration and swallowing in mind, pharmaceutical research has led to the development of oral disintegrating tablets (ODTs).

ODTs have been defined as “A solid dosage form containing medicinal substances which disintegrates rapidly, usually within a matter of seconds, when placed upon the tongue”. United States Food and Drug Administration further defines ODTs as solid oral preparations that disintegrate rapidly in the oral cavity, with an *invitro* disintegration time of approximately 30sec or less, when based on the United States Pharmacopeia (USP) disintegration test method or alternative. Research and development in the oral drug delivery segment has led to transition of dosage forms from simple conventional tablets/capsules to modified release tablets/capsules to oral disintegrating tablet (ODT) to wafer to the recent development of oral dissolving films (ODF). Basically the ODF can be considered as an ultra thin strip of postage stamp size with an active agent or active pharmaceutical ingredient and other excipients. The advantages of convenience of dosing and portability of ODF have led to wider acceptability of this dosage form by pediatric as well as geriatric population equally.

The ODTs in the market was accompanied by educating the mass about the proper way to administer the product like giving instructions “do

not swallow” or “do not chew”. The process of manipulating the ODT in oral or buccal cavity was also important. However since the ODT derived products were readily popular in the market in the form of breath-freshening strips, no further efforts were needed to instruct the populace about the technique of administration of this dosage form.

The manufacturing of ODF dosage form is cost effective with affordable end-products. From clinical aspect, the improved bioavailability can be advantageous in reducing the dose of the formulation. The product can be a substitute with more clinical advantages. However, not all drugs can be incorporated into this dosage form. The disadvantage of ODF is that high dose cannot be incorporated into the strip. Hence researchers have proven that the concentration level of active can be improved up to 50 percent/ dose weight. Novartis Consumer Health's Gas-X® thin strip has a loading of 62.5 mg of simethicone per strip.

Special features of mouth dissolving films:

- Thin elegant film
- Available in various sizes and shapes
- Unobstructive
- Fast disintegration
- Rapid release [3].

Advantages

1. Availability of larger surface area that leads to rapid disintegrating and dissolution in the oral cavity.
2. As compared to drops or syrup formulations, precision in the administered dose is ensured from each of the strips.
3. No need of water has led to better acceptability amongst the dysphagic patients. The difficulty encountered in swallowing tablets or capsules is circumvented. The large surface area available in the strip dosage form allows rapid wetting in the moist buccal environment. The dosage form can be consumed at anyplace and anytime as per convenience of the individual.
4. Since the first pass effect can be avoided, there can be reduction in the dose which

can lead to reduction in side effects associated with the molecule.

5. Patients suffering from dysphagia, repeated emesis, motion sickness, and mental disorders prefer this dosage form as they are unable to swallow large quantity of water.
6. The disadvantage of most ODT is that they are fragile and brittle, which warrants special package for protection during storage and transportation. Since the films are flexible they are not as fragile as most of the ODTs. Hence, there is ease of transportation and during consumer handling and storage.
7. The oral or buccal mucosa being highly vascularized, drugs can be absorbed directly and can enter the systemic circulation without undergoing first-pass hepatic metabolism. This advantage can be exploited in preparing products with improved oral bioavailability of the molecules that undergo first pass effect.

Disadvantages

1. High dose cannot be incorporated into the strip.
2. Drugs which are unstable at buccal pH cannot be administered.
3. Drugs which irritates the mucosa/have a bitter/unpleasant taste/an obnoxious odour cannot be administered.
4. Expensive packaging of oral film ^[4].

Ideal characteristics of a suitable drug candidate

1. The drug should have pleasant taste.
2. The drug to be incorporated should have low dose up to 40mg.
3. The drugs with small and moderate molecular weights are preferable.
4. The drug should have good stability and solubility in water as well as in saliva.
5. It should be partially unionized at the pH of oral cavity.
6. It should have the ability to permeate oral mucosal tissue.^[5]

The oral disintegration tablets (ODTs):

ODTs are sometimes difficult to carry, store and handle (fragility and friability).

Many ODTs are prepared by using the expensive lyophilisation process ^[6].

1. A large number of drugs can be formulated as mouth dissolving films. Innovative products may increase the therapeutic possibilities in the following indications.
2. Pediatrics (antitussives, expectorants, antiasthmatics)
3. Geriatrics (antiepileptic, expectorants)
4. Gastrointestinal disorders
5. Nausea due to cytostatic therapy)
6. Pain (migraine)
7. CNS (anti Parkinsonism therapy) ^[7].

A number of molecules can be incorporated into this delivery system. They may include cough/cold remedies (antitussives, expectorants), sore throat, and erectile dysfunction drugs, antihistaminic, antiasthmatics, gastrointestinal disorders, nausea, pain and CNS (e.g. anti-Parkinson's disease). Other applications comprise caffeine strips, snoring aid, multivitamins, sleeping aid etc. The ODF technology continues to be viewed as an alternative for ODT products that would afford a superior barrier to generic entry and product differentiation to over-the-counter brands. From the marketing perspective, a patented ODF technology would be beneficial. The grant of marketing exclusivity to the new dosage form would help to gain more revenue. As compared to the other ODTs such as tablets; the product is robust. From the patient point of view OS offers ease of administration and improved compliance.

COMPOSITION OF THE SYSTEM

Mouth dissolving film is a thin film with an area of 2-8 cm² containing an active ingredient. The immediate dissolution, in water or saliva respectively, is reached through a special matrix from water-soluble polymers. Drugs can be incorporated up to a single dose of 15mg. formulation considerations (plasticizers etc.) have been reported as important factors affecting mechanical properties of the films, such as shifting the glass transition temperature to lower temperature ^[6].

Table 1: A typical composition contains the following

Active pharmaceutical agent	5% to30% w/w
Water soluble polymer	45% w/w
Plasticizers	0-20% w/w
Surfactants	q. s.
Sweetening agent	3 to 6 % w/w
Saliva stimulating agents	2 to 6% w/w
Fillers, Colours & Flavours etc.	0-10% w/w

Table 2: List of drugs that can be incorporated in the oral strip

Drug	Dose	Therapeutic class
Chlorpheniramine maleate	4 mg	Anti allergic
Triprolidine hydrochloride	2.5 mg	Anti histaminic
Loperamide	2 mg	Anti diarrheal
Famotidine	10 mg	Antacid
Azatiidine maleate	1 mg	Anti histaminic
Zolmitriptan	2.5 mg	Anti migraine
Sumatriptan succinate	20-50 mg	Anti migraine
Ketoprofen	2mg	Analgesic
Nicotine	30 mg	Smoking cessation
Psuedoephedrine hydrochloride	8 mg	Bronchodilator
Acrivastine	10 mg	Anti histaminic

2) Water soluble polymers

Water-soluble polymers are used as film formers. The use of film forming polymers in dissolvable films has attracted considerable attention in medical and nutraceutical application. A variety of polymers can be used as alone or in combination of preparing films. These water-soluble polymers achieve rapid disintegration, good mouth feel and mechanical properties to the films. The disintegration rate of the polymers is decreased by increasing the molecular weight of polymer film bases. Some of the water soluble polymers used as film former are HPMC E-3 and K-3, Methyl cellulose A-3, A-6 and A-15,

Pullulan, carboxmethylcellulose cekol 30, Polyvinylpyrrolidone PVP K-90, Pectin, Gelatin, Sodium Alginate, Hdroypropylcellulose, Polyvinylalcohol, Maltodextrins and EUDRAGIT RD10. Polymerized rosin is a novel film forming polymer^[8].

3) Plasticizers

Plasticizer is a vital ingredient of the ODF formulation. It helps to improve the flexibility of the strip and reduces the brittleness of the strip. Plasticizer significantly improves the strip properties by reducing the glass transition temperature of the polymer. The selection of plasticizer will depend upon its compatibility with the polymer and also the type of solvent employed in the casting of strip. The flow of polymer will get better with the use of plasticizer and enhances the strength of the polymer^{[9],[10]}. Glycerol, Propylene glycol, low molecular weight polyethylene glycols, phthalate derivatives like dimethyl, diethyl and dibutyl phthalate, Citrate derivatives such as tributyl, triethyl, acetyl citrate, triacetin and castor oil are some of the commonly used plasticizer excipients. However inappropriate use of plasticizer may lead to film cracking, splitting and peeling of the strip^{[11],[12]}. It is also reported that the use of certain plasticizers may also affect the absorption rate of the drug^[13]. The Plasticizer employed should impart the permanent flexibility to the strip and it depends on the volatile nature plasticizer and the type of interaction with the polymer. It should be noted that the properties of plasticizer is important to decrease the glass transition temperature of polymer in the range of 40-60 °C for non aqueous solvent system and below 75 °C for aqueous systems^[14]. Plasticizer should be compatible with drug as well as other excipients used for preparation of strip. Cellulosic hydrophilic polymers were easily plasticized with hydroxyl containing plasticizers like PEG, propylene glycol, glycerol and polyols. In contrast, less hydrophilic cellulosic polymers were plasticized with esters of citric acid and phthalic acid. Glycerol acts as a better plasticizer for polyvinyl alcohol while diethylene glycol can be used for both hypromellose as well as polyvinyl alcohol films^[9].

4) Surfactants

Surfactants are used as solubilising or wetting or dispersing agent so that the film is getting dissolved within seconds and release active agent immediately. Some of the commonly used are sodium lauryl sulfate, benzalkonium chloride, bezthonium chloride, tweens etc. One of the most important surfactant is polaxamer407 that is used as solubilizing, wetting and dispersing agent [15].

4) Colouring agents

A full range of colouring agents are available, including FD&C, EU colours, natural colours and custom Pantone-matched colours. Some saliva stimulating agents may also be added to enhance the disintegration and to get rapid release. Some of these agents are citric acid, tartaric acid, malic acid, ascorbic acid and succinic acid [16].

5) Sweetening agents

Sweeteners have become the important part of the food products as well as pharmaceutical products intended to be disintegrated or dissolved in the oral cavity. The sweet taste in formulation is more important in case of pediatric population. Natural sweeteners as well as artificial sweeteners are used to improve the palatability of the mouth dissolving formulations. Suitable sweeteners include: (a) Water soluble natural sweetener: xylose, ribose, glucose, sucrose, maltose, stevioside etc., (b) Water soluble artificial sweetener: sodium or calcium saccharin salts, cyclamate salts, acesulfame-k etc., (c) Dipeptide based sweetener: aspartame and (d) Protein based sweeteners: thaumatin I and II. The sweetness of fructose is perceived rapidly in the mouth as compared to sucrose and dextrose. Fructose is sweeter than sorbitol and mannitol and thus used widely as a sweetener. Polyhydric alcohols such as sorbitol, mannitol, isomalt and maltitol can be used in combination as they additionally provide good mouth-feel and cooling sensation [17]. Aspartame was used for the preparation of oral strips of valdecoxib³¹. For the oral strip of piroxicam, maltodextrin was employed as sweetening agent [18]. Generally sweeteners are used in the

concentration of 3 to 6 %w/w either alone or in combination.

6) Saliva stimulating agent

The purpose of using saliva stimulating agents is to increase the rate of production of saliva that would aid in the faster disintegration of the rapid dissolving strip formulations. Generally acids which are used in the preparation of food can be utilized as salivary stimulants. Citric acid, malic acid, lactic acid, ascorbic acid and tartaric acid are the few examples of salivary stimulants, citric acid being the most preferred amongst them [17].

7) Flavouring agents

It was observed that age plays a significant role in the taste fondness. Flavouring agents can be selected from synthetic flavour oils, oleo resins, extract derived from various parts of the plants like leaves, fruits and flowers. Flavours can be used alone or in the combination. Peppermint oil, cinnamon oil, oil of nutmeg are examples of flavour oils while vanilla, cocoa, coffee, chocolate and citrus are fruity flavours. Apple, raspberry, cherry, pineapple are few examples of fruit essence type. The amount of flavour needed to mask the taste depends on the flavour type and its strength.

MANUFACTURING METHODS

One or combination of the following process can be used to manufacture the mouth dissolving films.

- i) Solvent casting
- ii) Semisolid casting
- iii) Hot melt extrusion
- iv) Solid dispersion extrusion
- v) Rolling

1) Solvent casting method

The ODF is preferably formulated using the solvent-casting method, whereby the water-soluble ingredients are dissolved to form a clear viscous solution. The API and other agents are dissolved in smaller amounts of the solution, and combined with the bulk. This mixture is then added to the aqueous viscous solution. The entrapped air is removed by vacuum. The resulting solution is cast as a film and allowed to

dry, which is then cut into pieces of the desired size. Water-soluble hydrocolloids used to prepare RDFs include: hydroxy propyl methylcellulose (HPMC), hydroxy propyl cellulose (HPC), pullulan, sodium alginate, pectin, carboxy methyl cellulose (CMC), polyvinyl alcohol (PVA). Misao Nishimura et al used following procedure to produce the fast disintegrating film of prochlorperazine by solvent casting techniques.

Specific types of equipment such as rollers are required for pouring the solution on an inert base. The clearance between the roller and the substrate determines the required thickness of the film. The final step, drying the film, removes the solvent and helps to obtain the finished product. Usually, glass, plastic or teflon plates are used as an inert base for film casting. When the manufacturing technology is transferred from laboratory scale to production scale, several problems can be encountered. These problems can include the casting of the film, obtaining uniform thickness of the film and proper drying of the sample. The selection of the proper type of dryer is important in the final step of drying. Once the films are dried, cutting, stripping, and packaging is done. Suitable size and shapes of films can be cut. The commonly available sizes of films are 3 x 2 cm² and 2 x 2 cm². Selection of the packaging container is an equally important parameter for the ODF. The packaging container should provide sufficient mechanical strength to protect the film during shipping and from external factors such as temperature and humidity. Depending upon the characteristics of the film, single-unit containers and multiple-unit dispensers can be selected. The packaged films are inspected before being packed into a secondary packaging container.

Water soluble ingredients are dissolved in water and API and other agents are dissolved in suitable solvent to form a clear viscous solution

Both the solutions are mixed

Degassed under vacuum

Resulting solution is cast as a film

Film is dried in drying oven and collected

Solvent casting system

Fig 1: Solvent casting system.

Advantages:

1. Great uniformity of thickness and great clarity then extrusion a typical relative standard deviation (RSD) for uniformity testing of an oral thin-film batch prepared by liquid casting is on the order of 1.2% RSD.
2. Film has fine gloss and freedom from defects such as die lines.
3. Films have more flexibility and better physical properties. The preferred finished film thickness is typically 10-100µm, although various thicknesses are possible to meet API loading and dissolution needs.

Disadvantages:

1. The polymer must be soluble in a volatile solvent or water.
2. A stable solution with a reasonable minimum solid content and viscosity should be formed.
3. Formation of a homogeneous film and release from the casting support must be possible.

2) Semisolid casting

In semisolid casting method firstly a solution of water soluble film forming polymer is prepared. The resulting solution is added to a solution of acid insoluble polymer (e.g. cellulose acetate phthalate, cellulose acetate butyrate), which was prepared in ammonium or sodium hydroxide. Then appropriate amount of plasticizer

is added so that a gel mass is obtained. Finally the gel mass is casted in to the films or ribbons using heat controlled drums. The thickness of the film is about 0.015-0.05 inches. The ratio of the acid insoluble polymer to film forming polymer should be 1:4 ^[19].

Solution of water soluble film forming polymer is prepared

Resulting solution is added to a solution of acid insoluble polymer

Appropriate amount of plasticizer is added so that gels mass is obtained

Finally the gel mass is casted in to the films or ribbons using heat controlled drums.

3) Hot melt extrusion

Usually, when designing RDFs, polymers with low molecular weight or viscosity, such as HPMC E5 or pullulan PI.20, are preferred. A combination of various grades of polymers may also be used to achieve desired physical properties. Mixing polymers of high and low viscosity produces a film with good mechanical strength and high drug solubility in the film.

The manufacturing process for the wafers in the pharmaceutical industry is divided into different steps. Generally, the mass is prepared first under the control of temperature and steering speed. Afterwards, the wafers are coated and dried in a drying tunnel, once again the temperature; air circulation and line speed are controlled. Then follows a slitting and in the last step the wafers are punched, pouched and sealed. Other ways of manufacturing oral wafers are spraying process or extrusion, in particular hot-melt extrusion ^{[20], [21]}.

Drug is mixed with carriers in solid form

The extruder having heaters melts the mixture

Finally the melt is shaped in films by the dies

Advantages:

- No need to use solvent or water.
- Fewer processing steps.
- Compressibility properties of the API may not be of importance.
- Good dispersion mechanism for poorly soluble drugs.
- More uniform dispersion of the fine particles because of intense mixing and agitation.
- Less energy compared with high shear methods.

Disadvantages:

- Thermal process so drug/polymer stability problem
- Flow properties of the polymer are essential to processing
- Limited number of available polymers.

4) Solid dispersion extrusion

In this method immiscible components are extrude with drug and then solid dispersions are prepared. Finally the solid dispersions are shaped in to films by means of dies. The drug is dissolved in a suitable liquid solvent. This solution is incorporated into the melt of polyols such as polyethylene glycol, obtained below 70 °C, without removing the liquid solvent. The selected solvent or dissolved drug may not be miscible with the melt of the polyethylene glycol. The polymorphic form of the drug precipitated in the solid dispersion may be affected by the liquid solvent use ^[19].

Drug is dissolved in a suitable liquid solvent

Then solution is incorporated into melt of polyethylene glycol, obtainable below 70oC

Finally the solid dispersions are shaped into the films by means of dies.

5) Rolling Method

In rolling method a solution or suspension containing drug is rolled on a carrier. The solvent is mainly water and mixture of water and alcohol.

The film is dried on the rollers and cutted in to desired shapes and size ^[19].

Prepare pre-mix with film forming polymer, polar solvent and other additives except a drug

Add pre mix to master batch feed tank

Fed it via a 1st metering pump and control valve to either or both of the 1st and 2nd mixer

Add required amount of drug to the desired mixer

Blend the drug with master batch pre mix to give a uniform matrix

Then a specific amount of uniform matrix is then fed to the pan through 2nd metering pumps.

The film is finally formed on the substrate and carried away via the support roller.

The wet film is then dried using controlled bottom drying.

TECHNOLOGIES:

Soluleaves:

SoluLeaves™ films have been designed to dissolve rapidly on contact with saliva, quickly releasing the active ingredients and flavours. These qualities make edible films an excellent delivery method for a large range of products requiring fast release in the mouth. For pharmaceutical uses this method of administration is particularly appropriate for paediatric or elderly patients, who may have difficulty swallowing traditional tablets or capsules. The delivery system can be used for low dosage applications such as the cough/cold, gastrointestinal and pain therapeutic areas, as well as delivering nutritional products. SoluLeaves™ films can also be designed to adhere to mucous membranes and to release the active ingredient slowly over 15

minutes. Similarly, the films can be used as a means of adding flavours to beverages either as a product or as a processing aid in manufacture.

Fig. 2: SoluLeaves

Features of Soluleaves:

- A vegetable based polymer film that carries low levels of active ingredients and flavouring
- Fast dissolution in the mouth
- Enhanced taste masking
- Enhanced convenience, portability and discreet format
- GMO and gelatin free (suitable for vegetarians, vegans and those with religious dietary restrictions)
- Sugar free variant suitable for diabetics
- Aqueous based and solvent free
- Application in a range of vitamins, flavourings, and pharmaceutical actives
- Suitable for paediatric and geriatric patients
- The SoluLeaves™ system is patented

WAFERTAB

WaferTab is a unique, innovative, highly stable edible film dose form. WaferTab™ is a drug delivery system that incorporates pharmaceutical actives into an ingestible film strip. The system provides rapid dissolution and release of actives when the strip comes into contact with saliva in the mouth.

Fig. 3: Watertab

FOAMBURST

FOAMBURST™ is a special variant of the SOLULEAVES™ technology where an inert gas is passed into the film during production. This result in a film with honey combed structure, which dissolves rapidly giving a novel mouth sensation. FOAMBURST™ has attracted interest from food and confectionary manufacturers as a means of carrying and releasing flavours.

XGEL

XGEL™ film is at the heart of Meldex International's intellectual property, used in all its film systems and its ingestible dosage delivery technologies. XGEL™ film provides unique product benefits for healthcare and pharmaceutical products: it is non animal-derived, approved on religious grounds and is suitable for vegetarians, the film is GMO free and continuous production processing provides an economic and competitive manufacturing platform. XGEL™ film can be taste masked, coloured, layered, and capable of being enteric properties whilst also having the ability to incorporate active pharmaceutical ingredients. The XGEL™ film systems can be made to encapsulate any oral dosage form, and can be soluble in either cold or hot water. XGEL™ film is comprised of a range of different water-soluble polymers, specifically optimised for the intended use.

EVALUATION PARAMETERS

- Mechanical properties:
 - Thickness
 - Dryness/tack test
 - Tensile strength
 - Percent elongation
 - Tear resistance
 - Young's modulus
 - Folding endurance
- Surface pH test
- Transparency
- Stickiness determination
- Disintegration time
- In-vitro dissolution test
- Assay/content uniformity
- Organoleptic evaluation
- Swelling property

- Swelling Index
- Morphology study
- Contact angle
- Stability testing

Thickness

It can be measured by micrometer screw gauge at different strategic locations. This is essential to ascertain uniformity in the thickness of the film as this is directly related to the accuracy of dose in the strip.

Dryness test/tack tests

About eight stages of film drying process have been identified and they are set-to-touch, dust-free, tack-free (surface dry), Dry-to touch, dry-hard, dry-through (dry-to-handle), dry-to-recoat and dry print-free. Although these tests are primarily used for paint films most of the studies can be adapted intricately to evaluate pharmaceutical OS as well. The details of evaluation of these parameters can be checked elsewhere and are beyond the scope of this review. Tack is the tenacity with which the strip adheres to an accessory (a piece of paper) that has been pressed into contact with the strip. Instruments are also available for this study.

Tensile strength

Tensile strength is the maximum stress applied to a point at which the strip specimen breaks⁴¹. It is calculated by the applied load at rupture divided by the cross-sectional area of the strip as given in the equation below:

$$\text{Tensile strength} = \frac{\text{Load at Failure} \times 100}{\text{Strip thickness} \times \text{Strip Width}}$$

Percent Elongation

When stress is applied, a strip sample stretches and this is referred to as strain. Strain is basically the deformation of strip divided by original dimension of the sample. Generally elongation of strip increases as the plasticizer content increases^[8].

$$\% \text{ Elongation} = \frac{\text{Increase in length of strip} \times 100}{\text{Initial length of strip}}$$

Tear resistance

Tear resistance of plastic film or sheeting is a complex function of its ultimate resistance to rupture. Basically very low rate of loading is employed and is designed to measure the force to initiate tearing. The maximum stress or force (that is generally found near the onset of tearing) required to tear the specimen is recorded as the tear resistance value in Newtons (or pounds-force).

Young's modulus

Young's modulus or elastic modulus is the measure of stiffness of strip. It is represented as the ratio of applied stress over strain in the region of elastic deformation as follows:

$$\text{Young's modulus} = \frac{\text{Slope} \times 100}{\text{Strip thickness} \times \text{Cross-head speed}}$$

Hard and brittle strips demonstrate a high tensile strength and Young's modulus with small elongation.

Folding endurance

Folding endurance is determined by repeated folding of the strip at the same place till the strip breaks. The number of times the film is folded without breaking is computed as the folding endurance value^[22].

Surface pH of the film

Surface pH of films is determined by placing the film on the surface of 1.5% w/v agar gel followed by placing pH paper (pH range 1-11) on films. The change in the color of pH paper was observed and reported.

Transparency test

The transparency of the films can be determined using a simple UV spectrophotometer. Cut the film samples into rectangles and placed on the internal side of the spectrophotometer cell. The determine transmittance of films at 600 nm. The transparency of the films was calculated as follows:

$$\text{Transparency} = (\log T_{600})/b = -\epsilon c$$

Where T₆₀₀ is transmittance at 600 nm and b the film thickness (mm) and c is concentration

Stickiness determination

It is evaluated by texture method usually used for measurement of the tack of pressure sensitive adhesives.

Disintegration time

The disintegration time limit of 30 s or less for orally disintegrating tablets described in CDER guidance can be applied to fast dissolving oral strips. Although, no official guidance is available for oral fast disintegrating films strips, this may be used as a qualitative guideline for quality control test or at development stage. Pharmacopoeial disintegrating test apparatus may be used for this study. Typical disintegration time for strips is 5–30s.

Dissolution test

Dissolution testing can be performed using the standard basket or paddle apparatus described in any of the pharmacopoeia. The dissolution medium will essentially be selected as per the sink conditions and highest dose of the API. Many times the dissolution test can be difficult due to tendency of the strip to float onto the dissolution medium when the paddle apparatus is employed.

Assay/drug content and content uniformity

This is determined by any standard assay method described for the particular API in any of the standard pharmacopoeia. Content uniformity is determined by estimating the API content in individual strip. Limit of content uniformity is 85–115 percent^[23].

Organoleptic evaluation

For evaluation of psychophysical evaluation of the product, special controlled human taste panels are used. *In vitro* methods of utilizing taste sensors, specially designed apparatus and drug release by modified pharmacopoeial methods are being used for this purpose. These *in vitro* taste assessment apparatus and methodologies are well suited for high-throughput taste screening of oral pharmaceutical formulations^[24].

Swelling property

The morphology of the films is studied using scanning electron microscopy (SEM), at a definite magnification¹¹. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) study refers the differences between upper and lower side of the films. It also helps in determination of the distribution of API. Near-infrared chemical imaging (NIR-CI) study helps in determining the difference between drug distributions in drug loaded films and recrystallization.

Film swelling studies is conducted using simulated saliva solution. Each film sample is weighed and placed in a preweighed stainless steel wire mesh. The mesh containing film sample is submerged into 15ml medium in a plastic container. Increase in the weight of the film was determined at preset time interval until a constant weight was observed^[25].

$$S.I = \frac{W_t - W_0}{W_0}$$

Where S.I is the swelling index, W_t is the weight of the film at time 't', and W_0 is the weight of film at $t = 0$.

Swelling Index:

It is useful in case of film formulation having gelling property and measured by 2 methods.

Linear Expansion Coefficient in Water: Film is immersed in water. Specimen is taken 2,4,6,8,10,15,30 and 60 seconds and the size of side length is measured. It is calculated as,

$$L\% = \frac{L_1 - L_0 * 100}{L_0}$$

Where

L_1 = Side length after immersion

L_0 = Side length before immersion

Amount Absorbed in Purified Water: The film is weighed (W_1) and put into the stainless steel mesh basket. The weight after immersion in water is measured (W_2). Similarly weight after immersion of basket without film (W_3). The amount absorbed (W) is determined by following equation,

$$W (g/g) = \frac{(W_2 - W_1 - W_3)}{W_1}$$

MORPHOLOGY STUDY CONTACT ANGLE

Contact angle measurements are performed at room temperature with a goniometer (AB Lorentzen and Wettre, Germany). A drop of double distilled water was placed on the surface of the dry film. Images of the water droplet were recorded within 10 seconds of deposition by means of digital camera. Digital pictures were analyzed by image J 1.28v software (NIH, USA) for angle determination. A minimum of five measurements, taken at different positions of the film, was carried out. The contact angle was measured on both sides of the drop and averaged^[26].

STABILITY TESTING

For stability testing the oral wafers were stored under controlled conditions of 25 °C / 60 % RH as well as 40 °C / 75 % over a period of 12 months according to the ICH guideline. During storage the oral wafers should be checked for their morphological properties, mass, thickness and reduction of film thickness, tensile properties, water content and dissolution behaviour. Consecutively, pH and content during storage are displayed^[27].

PACKING

A variety of packaging options are available for fast dissolving films. In the pharmaceutical industry it is vital that the package selected adequately preserve the integrity of the product. Single packaging is mandatory for films, which are pharmaceutical products; an aluminum pouch is the most commonly used. Applied Pharma Research (Switzerland)-Labtec GmbH of Germany has developed the Rapid Card, a proprietary and patented packaging system which is specifically designed for the mouth dissolving films. The Rapid Card is exactly the same size as a credit card and holds three mouth dissolving films on each side. Every dose can be taken out individually, allowing the patient to carry six single, packaged doses of his medication in his purse or wallet and have it readily available.

The material selected must have the following characteristics:

- They must protect the preparation from environment conditions.
- They must be FDA approved.
- They must be non-toxic.
- They must not be reactive with the product.
- They must not impart to product tasted or odors.
- They must meet applicable tamper-resistant requirement

Foil, paper or plastic pouches: The flexible pouch is a packaging concept capable of providing not only a package that is temper-resistance, but also by the proper selection of material, a package with a high degree of environmental protection. A flexible pouch is usually formed during the product filling operation by either vertical or horizontal forming, filling, or sealing equipment. The pouches can be single pouches or aluminum pouches.

Single pouch and aluminum pouch: Soluble film drug delivery pouch is a peel able pouch for “quick dissolve” soluble films with high barrier properties. The pouch is transparent for product display. Using a 2 structure combination allows for one side to be clear and the other to use a cost-effective foil lamination. The foil lamination has essentially zero transmission of both gas and moisture. The package provides a flexible thin film alternative for nutraceutical and pharmaceutical applications. The single dose pouch provides both product and dosage protection. Aluminum pouch is the most commonly used pouch.

Blister card with multiple units can be used. It consists of two components: the blister, which is the formed cavity that holds the product, and the lid stock, which is the material that seals to the blister. The material used to form the cavity is typically a plastic, which can be designed to protect the dosage form from moisture.

Barrier films are used where drug preparations are extremely sensitive to moisture. Several materials may be used to provide moisture protection such as polychlorotrifluoroethylene (PCTFE) film, polypropylene. Polypropylene does not stress crack under any conditions. It is an excellent gas and vapor barrier. Lack of clarity is still a drawback.

Conclusion:

Fast mouth dissolving films have several advantages over the conventional dosage forms. It is easy to carry and administration of the medicine so they are great importance during the emergency condition like asthmatic, allergy and migraine attacks when ever requires immediate action for controlling the diseases. The oral thin-film technology is still in the beginning stages and has bright future ahead because it fulfils all the need of patients.

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List of Some Marketed Products available as ODF^{[28], [29]}.

Brand name	Manufacturer/distributor or	API (strength)	Uses
Klonopin Wafers	Solvay Pharmaceuticals	Clonazepam (in five strengths: 0.125mg, 0.25 mg, 0.5 mg, 1 mg and 2 mg.)	Treatment of anxiety
Suppress®	InnoZen®, Inc.	Menthol (2.5 mg)	Cough suppressants
Theraflu	Novartis	Dextromethorphan HBR (15 mg)	Cough suppressant
Benadryl	Pfizer	Diphenhydramine HCl (12.5 mg or 25 mg)	Anti allergic
Orajel	Del	Menthol/pectin (2 mg/30 mg)	Mouth ulcer

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